

Studies on the Complexes Between 1, 2, 3-Butanetrione-1-Phenyl-2-Oxime and Common Metal Ions. Part-I

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The survey of literature reveals that complex formation by 1,2,3-butanetrione-1-phenyl-2-oxime with metal ions by precipitation method has been reported¹. However, no further investigation appears to be carried out.

All the chemicals used during this investigation were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade. pH adjustments were made on Beckmann pH meter model G with an accuracy ± 0.01 . Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Beckmann D.U. Spectrophotometer model G 2400 using one cm quartz cells. All the measurements were made at 25°.

*Preparation of the reagent*²: Benzoylacetone (16.2 gm, 0.1M) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (75 ml) and kept stirring in ice cold water bath. Solution of sodium nitrite (7.0 gm) in 50 ml of water was added drop by drop during 1 hr. Stirring was continued for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr more. The mixture was then kept for 2 hrs at room temperature. It was then diluted with water and the precipitated oxime was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol. Colourless prisms, m.p. 128°. Yield 13.4 gm i.e., 70%. It is soluble in ethanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, dioxane etc.

pH Study: 25 ml of $10^{-4}M$ Co^{2+} solution adjusted to the desired pH value (with hexamine up to pH 7, and with triethanolamine, above 7.0) were shaken with 10 ml of $10^{-2}M$ reagent in chloroform in a separating funnel. The optical density of coloured chloroform extract was measured at the time interval of 1.5 hr in each case so as to avoid some variation of intensity. λ_{max} for Co^{2+} -complex is 360 $m\mu$, but absorption by reagent being appreciable at this wavelength, O.Ds. were measured above 400 $m\mu$, where the reagent has no absorption. The study indicated that the extraction was maximum at pH 8.7. Therefore, pH, 8.7 was used for the further study in the determination of the nature of the extracted species.

Nature of the extracted species: The aqueous phase containing Co^{2+} was adjusted to different pH values in the range 7.5 to 8.8 with adequate buffers. At each pH value selected, O.Ds. of the chloroform extracts were recorded at 440 and 500 $m\mu$. The factor

$\log \frac{D}{D_0 - D}$ at each of the above wavelength was calculated, where D_0 represents the O.D. at the pH of maximum extraction (8.7) and D , the respective O.D. at other pH values.

A plot of $\log \frac{D}{D_0 - D}$ vs pH gave a slope $\simeq 2$ at 440 and 500 $m\mu$ (Fig. 1). This suggests

that the complex has a composition M : R as 1 : 2. Further confirmation of the above conclusion was obtained from the Job's method of continuous variation.

Fig. 1

Nature of species in alcohol-water medium: Job's method of continuous variation was used to study the nature of the species of the complex in alcohol-water medium in the ratio 60 : 40. $10^{-2} M$ concentration of both, Co^{2+} and reagent in alcohol were used keeping the total volume 25 ml. pH was maintained at 9.1 by adding buffer solution. Metal ion and reagent volumes were varied between 0 and 5 ml. Readings were taken after 1.5 hr at 400, 480 and 540 $m\mu$.

Corrected O.Ds. at various wavelengths were plotted against corresponding volumes of metal and reagent. From the plot, M : R ratio at different wavelengths appears to be different.

From these observations we feel, that, probably the complex is much dissociated and contains more than one species. It is also likely that the complex undergoes slow oxidation.

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